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IN THE SOUTH CAUCASUS

Institutional Challenges of Capitalist Transition in the South Caucasus
(1991–2024)

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Abstract

Armenia, Azerbaijan, and Georgia are in the Caucasus Mountains, south of Russia's boundaries. The South Caucasus republics have historically served as an economic and transportation "land bridge" connecting Europe to the Middle East and Asia, which the Russian Empire and others have sought to conquer at various times. Foreign investors have long been interested in Azerbaijan's oil and natural gas potential. Regional peoples may point to periods of autonomy or self-government in the past. Following the collapse of the Russian Empire in 1917, all three states declared independence, but all were re-conquered by Russia's Red (Communist) Army by early 1921. They regained their independence after the Soviet Union disintegrated at the end of 1991.

Key words: Capitalist reforms, South Caucasus, Azerbaijan, Armenia, Georgia, Türkiye, Russia, Political reforms, Economic situation, regional corridors, Governance, Economic development, Policy implications, Geopolitics, Post-Soviet transition, regional cooperation,

Market liberalization, Socioeconomic dynamics, Transition economies, Institutional changes,

Global impact, Comparative analysis

Post-Soviet Transition in the South Caucasus

South Caucasus nations and former Soviet Union members are undergoing a difficult transition. The transition to democratic systems and market economies in the Republics of Armenia, Azerbaijan, and Georgia need more changes as well as open-minded authorities and

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society. The move from a centrally planned to a market economy was not simple, and it needed strong political will and extensive economic changes in the South Caucasus republics. The boom years from 2000 to the global financial crisis obscured, to some degree, the region's fundamental inadequacy in two major areas: social policy concerns such as health, education, and gender equality, and private sector competitiveness. However, the 2009 financial crisis pushed these longstanding systemic issues to the fore.

Since 2008, the importance of the South Caucasus has been increased, after the EU Eastern Partnership policy was launched. The EU is committed to building strong and mutually beneficial relations with this region, irrespective of their individual level of ambition in their relations with the EU. The Association Agreements/Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Areas (AA/DCFTAs), concluded in 2014, have brought the relations between the EU and Georgia to a new level. These agreements aim at strengthening political association and economic integration and creating new opportunities in the region as increasing economic development.

South Caucasus is faced with the strategic Southern Gas Corridor. After completion, it will deliver Caspian-basin natural gas (first from Azerbaijan, and later perhaps from Turkmenistan, northern Iraq or other regional producers) via Azerbaijan, Georgia and Türkiye, to European markets in the Balkans and Italy.

Socially and politically- The South Caucasus is situated at the meeting point of the Russian Federation, Iran, Türkiye, Europe and Central Asia. The oil and gas reserves in the Caspian Sea and Central Asia and the pipelines to Europe through the South Caucasus East-West energy corridor emphasize the geopolitical importance of the region.

The transition from the Soviet system to pluralistic democratic societies and functioning market economies have been going through with political and social disruption, governance deficits, wars, occupation and conflicts in different regions. For the last two

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decades the three South Caucasus countries has experienced very deeply social distress, severe armed conflicts and territorial disputes, namely with regard to Nagorno-Karabakh, Abkhazia and South Ossetia/Tskhinvali Region and war against Russian Federation. Today there are still around 1.2 million internally displaced people (IDPs) and refugees in the three countries. Despite international mediation, the conflicts are still frozen. During the last decade, they remain unresolved and continue to hamper regional economic development and political stability.¹

Armenia: Remittance-Driven Growth and Isolation. Armenia remains completely isolated mainly because its borders with Azerbaijan and Türkiye are closed. The country has friendly relations with Iran and after joining to the Eurasian Economic Union, continues to depend economically and politically on the Russian Federation.

Due to regulatory reforms, an improved business environment and higher exports of commodities, Armenia's economy is slowly recovering. According to World Bank GDP (2015) is 10.561 \$billion. However, poverty and unemployment remain high, particularly in rural areas, and have risen much higher in recent years. Remittances from working migrants and the Armenian diaspora are critical sources of revenue for families and investments in the nation. Subsistence agriculture is the most important job sector, employing 45 percent of the working population. Market liberalization has imposed significant limits on the previously massively subsidized agriculture industry, and cooperating interests threaten fair competition. The political environment is difficult: Armenia is classified as 'partly free' by Freedom House, while the media is classified as 'not free'. The May 2012 parliamentary elections were marked by a competitive, energetic, and peaceful campaign.

¹ Gotsiridze, R. (2004). Georgia: Conflict regions and the economy. Central Asia and the Caucasus, (1 (25)).

Azerbaijan: Oil Boom and Diversification Struggles. Azerbaijan derives its revenues from oil and gas exports. Its considerable economic growth in the mid-2000s slowed down after 2006, partially due to reduced oil production. This reflects the high dependence of Azerbaijan's economy on natural resources. Pressure to diversify its economy is increasing. The non-oil sector, in particular construction, telecommunications and banking services, is steadily growing, however, it is mainly supported by oil-financed, unsustainable government spending. The agricultural sector employs 40% of the population but contributes only 5.2% to the gross domestic product (GDP). Azerbaijan was declared the world's top regulatory reformer in the World Bank's 2009 Doing Business Report, but competition is still hampered. While Azerbaijan is compliant with the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (EITI) and has introduced some formal anti-corruption measures, it continues to suffer from high perceived levels of corruption. The general Azerbaijani population is benefiting to some degree from the large revenues derived from natural resources. This positive development is reflected in the country's decreasing poverty rate, from 43.7% in 2003 to 7.6% in 2011². Also, the Azerbaijani economy has been dealing with refugee and IDP issues until today, after the restoration of territorial integrity. And a new and great challenge occurred for Azerbaijan: the restoration of liberated and totally devastated territories from Armenian occupation.

Georgia: Pro-Western Reforms and Conflict Legacy. Since the fall of the Soviet Union and the declaration of its independence, Georgia has had an extraordinarily damaged and difficult period of growth. During the fiscal year, it was involved in two ethno-conflicts in different sections of the state, both of which were fueled by Russia. Georgia was compelled to

² Suleymanov, E. (2008). The Cooperation Strategy of World Bank with Azerbaijan Republic. Available at SSRN 2170996.

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forge new business ties and find new partners. Since that time, Georgia has maintained a pro-Western foreign policy. Georgia is presently making strides toward Euro Atlantic integration. It has the most extensive ties with the EU, apart from its neighbors.

Nonetheless, Freedom House categorized Georgia as 'partly free' in 2012. The lack of independence of the judiciary is a major cause of concern. Armed confrontation with the Russian Federation in 2008, paired with the subsequent economic crisis, pushed the country into a deep recession. The Georgian economy, on the other hand, has gradually recovered in recent years, with a growth rate of more than 5%. According to the World Bank, the GDP for 2015 is 13.965 billion dollars. Major reforms, particularly in social services, are being conducted from a neoliberal standpoint. Agriculture, which employs over half of the working population, is one of the industries with the most potential for growth. Rural poverty will remain a big concern in Georgia in the next years. Income gaps are widening, and the country has the highest Gini index (4.160) in the area (2015).³ Although the living conditions of IDPs are increasingly improving, many of them are still unable to fully exercise their social and economic rights and confront a lack of employment opportunities. IDPs are the most vulnerable segment of Georgia's population. The parliamentary elections in October 2012 represented Georgia's first democratic transfer of power in post-Soviet history, culminating in the president and prime minister co-governing (called cohabitation). According to the new coalition administration, it plans to promote Euro-Atlantic integration, rural development, and greater economic ties with Russia. After negotiating Association Agreements/Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Agreements with the EU, Georgia maintains a visa-free system with the Schengen region.

³ Georgieva, S. V., Kapanadze, D., Jijelava, D., Lukic, J., Jikia, L., Kaviladze, I., ... & De Abreu Ferreira, S. (2020). Analysis of Gaps between National Legislation of Georgia and World Bank Environmental and Social Framework.

Regional Fragmentation and Conflict. The South Caucasus witnessed complete economic fragmentation following the disintegration of the Soviet Union. The cooperation links of firms and states connecting the various areas of the former Soviet Union shrank considerably. On the other hand, certain commercial alliances were exploited to exert political pressure. Former Soviet states were forced to establish new commercial links and agreements. Furthermore, the political elites were actively engaged in the construction of ethnically defined nation states, notwithstanding the difficult war for power. They also compete for control of the newly independent states' economic resources. These processes were accentuated in the South Caucasus by nationalistic language and practices that resulted in deadly confrontations.

One of those conflicts has been over the Nagorno-Karabakh region between Armenia and Azerbaijan, which was totally solved in 2023 by a successful anti-terroristic operation by Azerbaijan. Türkiye closed the rail and air connections with Armenia and halted the transit of humanitarian aid through its territory to Armenia in 1993. Today, Armenia has two “gates” to the world: Georgia to the north and Iran to the south. These “gates” are inappropriate for the establishment of regional economic cooperation and the implementation of transnational projects. Out of the 1,500 kilometers of land border that Armenia shares with its four neighbors, only about 250 kilometers are open for transnational economic relations. Armenia has well-established relations with Georgia and their current economic ties are crucially important for Armenia, as Georgia is the main transit country for Armenia. Iran and Armenia have developed energy and trade cooperation even though Armenia’s major trade and economic partner for either state or private business actors is Russia. With an active flow of remittances and investments from Russia, its role in Armenia’s economy is major. Recently Armenia deepened its economic integration with Russia within the framework of the EAEU, along with Belarus, Kazakhstan, and Kyrgyzstan. In this context, Armenia could potentially benefit from new opportunities by gaining access to the EAEU markets. But the coming of N.Pashinyan to power

and more west-oriented policies had deteriorated ties with Russia. And there is a new opportunity for all Caucasus Zangazur Corridor⁴, if they achieve. On the other hand, Armenian businesses have almost one-sided economic relations with their Turkish counterparts. Goods from Türkiye enter Armenia, but no major trade flows are going from Armenia to Türkiye. Georgia plays a significant role in the socio-economic relations of the South Caucasus since it is the transit country for regional transport and energy projects. Currently, Georgia has substantial socio-economic cooperation with all neighboring countries.

Economic Cooperation and Megaprojects. There are various motivations for economic cooperation between countries in the South Caucasus. Economic factors, historical links, cultural ties, and social factors are stimulating and necessitating economic cooperation between countries. In addition to this, the geographical proximity and unity of the countries in the region are conducive and encouraging factors for the formation of economic cooperation agreements. Although, there are no economic or diplomatic relations between Azerbaijan and Armenia. It means that Armenia does not participate in any regional or transitional projects. It has resulted during the formation of a new East-West Silk Road through Georgia to Europe via Türkiye. As a network of major present transportation corridors, Azerbaijan and Georgia are becoming vital transit links between East and West. The economic cooperation between Azerbaijan, Türkiye and Georgia has been developed through mega projects in energy transportation. There is free trade agreement between Türkiye and Georgia now. As well, Georgia and Türkiye have visa-free regime for their citizens. All of these three countries are trying to benefit from the recent regional connectivity initiatives to boost trade, increase foreign direct investments and growth their economies. Azerbaijan has borders with

⁴ Gawliczek, P., & Iskandarov, K. (2023). The Zangezur corridor as part of the global transport route (against the backdrop of power games in the South Caucasus region). *Security and Defence Quarterly*, 41(1), 36-53.

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Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan via the Caspian Sea and it has land borders with Georgia, Russia, Iran, Armenia, and Türkiye. Azerbaijan's cooperation with Georgia and Türkiye is focused on natural resources and excludes Armenia due to the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict. Azerbaijan has the richest oil and gas reserves in the region and therefore plays an important role in major energy projects. Access to these resources explains the Azerbaijani regime's claim for a leading role in the South Caucasus and its attempts to influence the policies of the big neighbors, particularly those of Türkiye and Georgia. In particular, Azerbaijan is one of the sponsors of the East-West and North-South transport corridors. This effort will require improvements in infrastructure and logistics performance for trans-border trade. The rich oil and gas reserves of Azerbaijan and its purposeful policy have created opportunities for doing huge amount of works in the energy sphere as well. If we look through the energy security issue, it is clearly seen that Azerbaijan already plays an important role in the energy security of Europe. Azerbaijan has large gas reserves, and in September 2014 BP began construction of the Southern Gas Corridor to supply Europe directly by 2019, bypassing Russia. From this standpoint, starting the implementation of the "Southern Gas Corridor" project has been a historic event. Caspian oil is now flowing through a pipeline running from Baku through Georgia to the Turkish port of Ceyhan, providing western countries with ready access to a vast new source of supply.

Azerbaijan's transportation infrastructure development is likewise a top focus. It is now reconstructing the ancient Silk Road with the use of new technology and the cooperation of adjacent nations. The Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway, which runs from Azerbaijan through Georgia and into Türkiye, is currently under development and will connect Azerbaijan with Europe by train for the first time.

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The Baku-Tbilisi-Kars Railway is a new railway route that connects Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Türkiye. The project began in 2007, and building began in 2008. It calls for the restoration and reconstruction of a 178-kilometer-long railway between Marabda and Akhalkalaki, as well as the construction of a new railway from Akhalkalaki to the Turkish border. The Kars-Akhalkalaki route is scheduled to completely replace the defunct Kars-Gyumri-Tbilisi line, which was the USSR's only rail access to Türkiye. After Armenian Turkish ties worsened as a result of the Armenian Azerbaijani war in Karabakh, Istanbul unilaterally banned trade on this route. This project would essentially create a new rail-only corridor from the Caspian marine to Europe via Türkiye, eventually eliminating the need for marine transit once the proposed rail tunnel across the Bosphorus Strait in Istanbul is completed. When the railway is completely operational, all three nations will profit from enhanced trade and economic links as well as extra Foreign Direct Investments (FDI) via the new railway connecting Europe and Asia. According to Georgia's international interest, the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars Railway is projected to boost Georgia's role as a transit country while also forging strategic alliances with Türkiye and Azerbaijan. Other advantages are promised by the Kars-Akhalkalaki-Baku railway route for Georgia. In addition, the railway line is the only direct land connection between Baku and Istanbul. Analysts believe the railway has the potential to lure freight, particularly oil, from Central Asia to Türkiye by providing an additional outlet to the sea. Caspian traders have the option of delivering their oil straight to European buyers by train. They will undoubtedly save money and time if they avoid tanker routes around the Black Sea. Georgia might provide two distinct oil transit routes to Europe, one by sea and one by land. It is transforming the nation into an essential element of the transportation corridor connecting Asia, the Caucasus, and Europe. The Baku-Tbilisi-Kars project, which promotes passenger and cargo movement between Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Türkiye, was completed in early 2017.

Comparative Analysis of Reforms. There are intriguing features if we look at the key capitalist advances and reforms in three nations in the area. In case of Armenia- In 2008, the economic growth rate in Armenia slowed down significantly. In 2007 it was 13.8% and projections for 2008 were between 8% and 10% prior to the crisis. The global crises reached Armenia in the third and fourth quarters of 2008; overall, the economy recorded only 6.8% growth. In 2008 growth projections for 2009 were at around 8%, but the economy plummeted 14.6%. The economic decline for the EESC countries was 8.5% (excluding Azerbaijan). Armenia is the only country of the group for which annual growth ranks as low as that of Ukraine for 2009 (-15%).

By the end of 2009 and early 2010, prospects brightened, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the Government of Armenia (GoA) suggested 1.2% growth for 2010, but after the economy registered 5.5% in the first quarter the projections were corrected to 5.3%. According to official statistics, remittances contribute to around 20% of total GDP. In reality, however, this figure could easily rise to half of GDP, when considering that one third of total remittances are being sent through informal channels (World Bank), so lower remittance inflows would explain part of the GDP drop linked to the crisis.

Inflation was low in 2009 at 3.4% compared to 9% in 2008, as a result of declining incomes and demand. With the signs of recovery in early 2010, the consumer price index started to grow steadily, reaching 8% (in comparison with the same period of 2009) in April 2010.

Investments in the construction sector powered by remittances and to some extent by FDI provided the basis for growth, leading private transfers to Armenia to be correlated with real estate prices. FDI increased from USD 104 million in 2000 to USD 935 million in 2008, while remittances, according to official figures, grew from USD 761 million in 2004 to USD

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2.3 billion in 2008 (USD 1.6 billion in 2009). According to the World Bank Migration and Remittances Factbook 2011, remittances inflows declined to USD 0.7 billion in 2009 and should amount to USD 0.8 billion in 2010 (World Bank, 2011).

The passage of the "Peasant and Peasant Collective Farms Law" and the "Land Law" in February 1991 established the institutional foundation for Armenia's agriculture industry, which was followed by legislation for land privatization. Individual farmers received 70% of arable land, while the remaining was leased to farmers as reserved state property. The bulk of these leases are for one to three years and are for hay fields and pastures. This governmental reserve property was to be sold in larger quantities to private farmers later on. Following this wave of privatization, over 300,000 farms were established, a figure that has remained consistent. Only 3% of farms are owned by commercial organizations, with the remainder owned by individuals. According to a study conducted in early 1998, around 60% of farms are between 0.5 and 2.5 hectares in size, with a median farm size of 1.5 hectares (NSS, FAO). When state-owned land was handed to local governments in 2004–05, there was a significant institutional shift in terms of land property rights. The communities now have the authority to sell, lease, or manage the land. Since joining the World Trade Organization (WTO) in 2003, Armenia has worked to enhance its regulatory framework, institutional structure, sanitary and phytosanitary control, consumer protection (food safety), and other sectors in accordance with WTO criteria.

Armenia is now in the process of harmonizing sanitary, phytosanitary, and veterinary controls with the CIS nations. An intergovernmental agricultural council has been established to coordinate actions aimed at integrating the agricultural sectors of the CIS nations. Armenia has a considerable potential for manufacturing organic goods that are competitive due to favorable climatic conditions and low land and labor expenses. On April 8, 2008, the law "On Organic Agriculture" was enacted to regulate the production, preservation, processing,

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transportation, and sale of agricultural products, as well as to define the principles of organic agriculture management: improvement of soil qualities, ensuring maximum preservation of the biological value of agricultural foodstuffs in processing, and elimination of environmental pollution (use of synthetic chemical substances) and genetically modified crops. The law also provides governmental assistance to organic agriculture by supporting the introduction of innovations and contemporary technologies; organizing business forums and fairs to promote inter-country cooperation and foster exports; and subsidizing "target projects." Agriculture was designated as a priority sector in 2010. The strategy and implementation plan for 2010–20 agricultural sustainable development were discussed in February 2010. A notable government endeavor has been a plan to establish a free economic zone near Yerevan International Airport to aid in the export of agricultural goods. The approach envisions complete integration of the production-processing-marketing relationship. According to estimates, the initiative will result in a 20% rise in Armenian agricultural product exports (primarily to Russia and the European Union [EU]) within a year of implementation. The export value of agricultural goods in 2009 was USD 19 million. Armenia has been confronted with a problematic phenomenon: a rising economy with a worsening trade balance, farmers' actual earnings stagnating, and unproductive agricultural operations. In the absence of competent agricultural policy, there is a serious risk of small farm liquidation. Because the rural sector was left out of economic growth until 2008, and despite an increase in average monthly nominal wages in agriculture from AMD 30 000 to AMD 69 000, farmers would be better off engaging in other economic activities or seeking better opportunities as migrant workers (mostly to Russia), as their absolute amount of income is very low. The following issues continue to plague Armenian agriculture: poor irrigation network condition, climate dependency, inability to purchase quality seeds, chemicals, and diesel fuel, lack of agricultural equipment, lack of quality roads, low purchasing prices, high veterinary service costs, and lack of access to technical

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information and technology. Armenia had a specialized collective-based agriculture during the Soviet era, which collapsed as a result of the privatization process, with deterioration of land, labor, companies, and technology. As a result, successful agricultural policy faces a number of issues, including communal pasture management, excessive fragmentation of existing peasant farms, creating sustainable land management, and developing strategies to modernize agricultural output. Armenia still needs an efficient agriculture strategy to maintain food self-sufficiency and a favorable trade balance. Consolidation, specialization, and commercialization strategies must be created. Agriculture's commercial organization share is minimal and had already been declining prior to the crisis, falling from 3.8% in 2004 to 2.8% of total commercial organizations in 2008. It would therefore be able to boost yield and productivity through consolidation and commercialization. Finally, special attention should be paid to infrastructure concerns such as irrigation, roads, and communication in order to boost production, sales, and hence revenue.⁵

One thing is clear when looking at Azerbaijan: its reliance on hydrocarbon-based exports. Since 1996, Azerbaijan has experienced macroeconomic stability and dynamic economic development. A number of significant policies, to be developed further, have been implemented to promote socio-economic development, with a high priority on oil strategy with the development of the Caspian energy resources. Since the “Contract of the Century”¹, signed in 1994 between the State Oil Company of Azerbaijan Republic (SOCAR) and the Western Oil Consortium to develop Azerbaijan’s Caspian oil reserves (Azeri-Chirag-Gunashli), the level of foreign and domestic investment in Azerbaijan from 2004 to 2009 amounted to USD 70 billion, half of which was foreign investments. Macroeconomic stability was therefore

⁵ Sandoyana, E. M., Voskanyan, M. A., & Galstyan, A. G. (2022). Main Drivers of Economic Growth in Armenia: Analysis and Evaluation. *Finance: Theory and Practice*, 26(4), 44-59.

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achieved as a result of the entrance of oil giants in the domestic market. Processes to create acceptable economic infrastructure and adopt new laws regulating the business environment were initiated as early as in 1993, under former President Haydar Aliyev.

Despite the positive macroeconomic results, there are still a number of problems to be tackled, especially the improvement of the economic and social situation of the population, fairer distribution of incomes, the reduction of unemployment and the diversification of the economy.

The economy of Azerbaijan, in many respects, still depends on the extraction of hydrocarbons. With the growing volumes of receipts from oil exports and the inadequacy of monetary instruments available to the government, controlling inflation and excessive evaluation of the national currency have become major problems.

Azerbaijan's dependence on the oil sector leads to fears of Dutch Disease: negative economic consequences arising from natural-resource price increases with a negative effect on industrial and manufacturing development. Moreover, forecasts led by British Petroleum and SOCAR have shown the peak of extraction of these resources in Azerbaijan to be reached in 2014 (OECD/IEA, 2010), leading to the exhaustion of possibilities of extensive growth. In parallel, the global economic recession of 2008-09 emphasizes vulnerability to international energy shocks, in a country where more than 90% of all exports are oil-related, raising issues of diversification and the development of non-oil sectors. Hence, it is necessary now to involve new resources for steady economic growth, such as processing industries.

Azerbaijan's economy has fundamentally changed since 2006, when oil started to be dispatched through the Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan (BTC) pipeline, as a new phase of development was implemented and oil revenues began to flow. Industry, construction and services showed strong turnover and wage growth. Foreign currency inflows (US dollar) boosted the state budget and fueled inflation – which averaged 18% in 2007-08. The role of the state oil fund,

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SOFAZ, during this period allowed a tight control of revenues and expenditures in the oil sector, which prevented Dutch Disease. The rise in oil prices allowed the government to engage in large-scale infrastructure projects to pave the way for the non-oil sectors; a real challenge for the country's future development. The government has engaged in important modernization of social services programs, mostly since 2000, which have played a vital role in reducing poverty. With the major expenditures of SOCAR being transferred to the state budget (50% of budget revenues), the government was able to increase pensions and wages and to invest in schools, universities, and hospitals. Consequently, poverty decreased significantly from 49% to 11.2% between 2001 and 2009. The national poverty line indicator increased by 3.7 times from 24 Azerbaijani manat (AZN) to AZN 89.5 over the same period. Although the country managed to record positive growth in 2009, nearly all macroeconomic indicators were affected by the global downturn. For the first time, the country was forced to increase production for less profit, which is a distinctive feature of raw materials exporting to countries. If the crisis had not taken place, annual nominal GDP was forecast to increase by an additional AZN 4 billion in 2009. The reduction of the nominal GDP to AZN 34.6 billion was caused by falling oil prices and moderate rates of non-oil sector development. Indeed, the oil sector contributed to a rise of 14.3% of GDP, while the non-oil sector contributed only 3.2%. Azerbaijan returned to high growth in the second half of 2009 with an increasing oil price. Therefore, the country's GDP increased by 9.3%, while forecasts made by the IMF for 2010 and 2011 show growth of 7.5% and 4.1%, respectively, the highest in the Black Sea region. GDP per capita grew by 7.9% in 2009, amounting to AZN 3 917.3, before decreasing to AZN 2 539.9 in January–November 2010. According to the International Monetary Fund (IMF), per capita GDP in parity purchase power (PPP) terms for 2000–08 increased by 3.9 times and reached the level of USD 8,600, which is very high for a transition country (IMF, 2009). Consequently, the end

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of the “transition period” was officially announced by President Ilham Aliyev in the first quarter of 2010.⁶

Azerbaijan's GDP (gross domestic product) increased by 4.3% in 2010 compared to 9.3% in 2009; GDP growth in 2010 was 6% in current prices. The country is less involved in the global economy and was not as seriously affected by the worldwide crisis as other Eastern Europe and South Caucasus (EESC) nations such as Ukraine, which had a 15% contraction. The government's assistance to banks and ongoing pledges to infrastructure projects also helped to reduce the crisis's impact. Nonetheless, the reduction in oil returns in the first half of 2009 underscored Azerbaijan's susceptibility to energy shocks and the risk of relying on commodity exports. Some industries, such as construction and metallurgy, reported major challenges in 2009. Despite this, practically all industries expanded. Furthermore, non-oil production accounted for 45.5% of total output, with a 3.2% increase. In 2010, the non-oil industry accounted for 42.4% of total GDP, representing a roughly 6% yearly rise in value.

Since 1995, the government has made genuine attempts to grow the industry by particular policies and programs, as well as by providing funding from the state budget. As a result of significant structural changes in agriculture, state farms and collectives were liquidated, and their property was split among their members. Farmers' earnings grew and poverty decreased as a result of the shift to a market economy and a new type of property. Though land distribution was a first step toward access to funding, additional favorable conditions are required for the industry to completely thrive.

The government's "State Programme on Social-Economic Development of the Regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan," which went into effect in 2009-13, and the "State Programme

⁶ Suleymanov, Elchin, and Khatai Aliyev. "Macroeconomic analysis and graphical interpretation of Azerbaijan economy in 1991-2012." *Expert Journal of Economics* 3.1 (2015).

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on Reliable Provision of Food to the Population in the Azerbaijan Republic," which was adopted in 2008 and implemented in 2009-15, are primarily aimed at achieving food security and rural development.⁷

The government founded the "Agroleasing" Open Stock Company in 2004 to boost agricultural producers' material and technological bases and to provide agro-technical services. Farmers, in particular, can use the firm to obtain agricultural gear, fertilizer, and thoroughbred animals. For loans, pricing for equipment and machinery, and large-scale projects, the corporation offers gentler terms than the market.

Since 2006, the government has taken many measures and implemented state programs to integrate into the international system, improve transportation potential, and encourage competitiveness. According to the World Bank, the government expected to expedite regional and local road reconstruction beginning in 2008. The bank also anticipated that over the next 10 years, around USD 1.1 billion will be required yearly to improve infrastructure utilities and public services.

From 63% in 2000 to 87% in 2008, the private sector's share of construction climbed from 63% to 87%. However, between 2002 and 2005, it averaged 95%. The construction industry is constrained by the state's big involvement, a massive regulatory load, and a lack of competition. Construction permit requirements must be eased in order to attract more investment and create a more competitive environment.

There is also opportunity for the oil and gas business, which can meet demand for basic equipment and machinery, metalworking, technical services, transportation, food, and the chemical and petrochemical industries. Local businesses will need to meet international

⁷ Aras, O. N., Suleymanov, E., & Mammadov, K. (2016). Economy of Azerbaijan: 25 years of independence. Sharg-Garb.

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standards, which will include strong capital resources, enhanced delivery requirements, and increased ability to handle huge orders.

In the final state of the S.Caucasus , Georgia, which remains a territorially violated country by Russia. Since 2003, the government has carried out a large number of reforms to create competitive market conditions and a business-enabling environment to attract foreign direct investment (FDI). The reforms also aimed at trade liberalization and eradicating corruption. The spectacular growth of 9.7% on average from 2003 to 2008 fueled a significant increase in tax collection (and thus in tax to GDP ratio) thanks to a simplification of the tax system, a rapidly improving business climate led by increased privatization of state-owned assets and reduced bureaucracy, increased FDI inflows, and high international and domestic demand. At the same time, however, imports rose twice as much as exports, increasing the current account deficit. The August 2008 war, followed by an economic crisis, put a stop to this prosperous period. By the end of August, many buildings and infrastructures were destroyed, and more than 100,000 people were displaced. Less than a month later, the overheating of the economy and the onset of the global crisis led to a strong fall in both national and international demand and FDI flows world-wide. These developments have highlighted the weaknesses of the Georgian economy in terms of education (skill gap), technology availability, modernization and mechanization, and SME financing (poor financial background). The government's agricultural policy focuses on the creation of agricultural and food-processing enterprises through subsidized purchases of land, privatizations, allocations for livestock breeding, agricultural machinery, and irrigation infrastructure, the abolition of several taxes, and access to credit and technology. Several policies have been adopted since 2005. In 2009, the government even implemented 60 projects for clean water and irrigation systems worth GEL 58,860,754 (according to the Ministry of Infrastructure). In order to attract

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capital, the “Law on Privatization of Agricultural Land Existing in State Ownership” entered into force in July 2005 and is still ongoing. Its main objective is to create large farms. The remaining 360 000 ha of state-owned agricultural land was considered for privatization, with a minimum land area of 3 ha per purchase. The process is supervised by the Ministry of Economic Development of Georgia and its regional offices. Non-leased, state-owned lands are subject to special auctions (followed by open auctions) for Georgian nationals, individuals, or communities. On the other hand, leased agricultural land is subject to direct sales or direct sales under competition and is not bound by the buyer’s origin. To attract further foreign capital, tax cuts were allowed by the government, which, under the liberalization of the tax system, abolished taxes on property (on plots smaller than five ha), property transactions, profit tax, VAT on the primary supply of agricultural products, and import duty on agricultural equipment.⁸ The project “100 New Enterprises in Rural Areas” was launched in 2008 for a year. Its main objective was to target rural employment and create jobs by facilitating the establishment of rural enterprises and exports. Entrepreneurs are allowed to purchase state-owned agricultural land at preferential prices on the condition that they foster infrastructure development and employment. By mid-2010, four projects had been developed for a total of GEL 15 million, half from domestic and half from foreign capital. The “Cheap Credit” program was also launched in 2008 and is supervised by the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development. The program aims at enterprise development in agriculture, recycling, and tourism, promoting easier access to credit at lower interest rates and long maturity terms⁹. Loans are issued on favorable terms with grace periods, lower interest rates, and longer terms. That year, 117 projects were financed by this initiative for a total of GEL 62.4 million, of which GEL 27.6 million were allocated to 37 agricultural companies (mainly in fruits and vegetables,

⁸ Andronova, I. V., & Katamadze, A. (2018). Transformation of the economic policy of Georgia. *RUDN Journal of Economics*, 26(2), 212-223.

⁹ Kasradze, T., & Zarnadze, N. (2019). Challenges of Economic of Georgia: Good and Bad Economic Growth. *European Journal of Economics and Business Studies*, 5(1), 178-186.

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tea, poultry, and juice, nuts and grain processing, dairy, and meat-collecting companies) for approximately 25,800 beneficiaries (the Ministry's primary estimates). In 2009, 17 new projects were financed for a total of GEL 2.5 million, out of the allocated GEL 20 million. A final measure was due to enter into force in 2009, following the crisis. The Agricultural Development Strategy (2009–10) was aimed at fostering food safety, modernizing machinery, and promoting organic farming but was not approved by the government. The next steps in the agricultural sector are: ▪ Increasing effectiveness and commercialization of the agricultural sector, the direct share of the average farming enterprises in the agricultural sector. By 2015, agriculture products' exports are to be brought up to 25% of the total, and lands supplied with irrigation systems will be enlarged 2.5 times (from 130 000 to 300 000 hectares). ▪ More than 200 enterprises for processing agricultural products will be created; more than 10 000 people will be employed, and about 100 000 people will be involved in the process. The development of the agricultural sector will enhance the successful implementation of the governmental program "100 New Processing Plants in Rural Areas." The Georgian government has started the process of harmonizing its legislation with EU food law, compatible both with the EU and the WTO, and developing secondary legislation to ensure its enforcement and smooth operation. The "Law of Georgia on Food Safety and Quality" was adopted in December 2005. Due to the fragmented structure of the agro-food sector and the important role of household agriculture in ensuring food security, it was decided to exclude small and artisanal food-processing firms from the list of those under the official control of food safety due to the fragility of their businesses.¹⁰

¹⁰ Abesadze, N. (2014). The main trends of integration of Georgia into the world economic system. *Procedia-Social and behavioral sciences*, 156, 166-169.

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Conclusion. In this paper, we analyzed the existing capitalist reformable situation in the South Caucasus, as well as the potential for regional cooperation and integration. The essay diversified various strategic directions, which would have important implications for the future growth of this region; nonetheless, it is dependent on European security policy as well as global trade routes.

Given recent economic developments and attempts toward economic integration between Azerbaijan, Türkiye, and Georgia, as well as other megaprojects from Central Asia to Europe that make the South Caucasus a transit region, this transportation corridor has emerged as a new strategic and significant one for Western and European countries in terms of energy security policy.

Convinced that regional economic cooperation may be a significant step toward conflict transformation in the South Caucasus, this article advises that the potential for such integration be studied. The South Caucasus, which serves as a bridge between Europe and Central Asia, has gained strategic importance as a result of large pipeline projects bringing crude oil and natural gas from Central Asia, the Caspian, and Iran to Europe.

Today, the Caucasus stands at their own crossroads. Once again, global forces beyond its control are gathering on the horizon. The path of continued market-oriented reforms may seem difficult because it requires changes to established ways of doing business and governing. But it's the surest way to insulate your economies against future shocks and to enjoy the huge upsides of private sector led growth where the role of the state is to be a facilitator and enabler but not the driver.

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